

ENDOPHYTIC N₂ FIXING MICROBIAL LIQUID CONSORTIUM FOR SUGARCANE CROP

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Abstract

Interest of liquid biofertilizer formulations is growing rapidly all over the world since the liquid biofertilizers of good quality holds great promise in agriculture over the conventional carrier based biofertilizers. With the view to isolate endophytic bacteria and to assess their functional potential in relation to N₂ fixation in sugarcane crop was undertaken. A total of 77 endophytic nitrogen fixing bacterial isolates were obtained from different sugar recovery zones of Western Maharashtra and screened on the selective culture media by enrichment culture technique. All endophytic isolates were tested for different morphological and biochemical tests. Based on the morphological and biochemical characterization, the isolates were tentatively identified as *Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus*, *Burkholderia* spp., *Herbaspirillum* spp., *Azoarcus* spp. and *Azospirillum* spp. A common medium was formulated for mass production of all these N₂ fixing bacterial endophytes as a liquid consortium. The functional diversity for N₂ fixation ability of all the endophytic bacteria was determined by Acetylene Reduction Assay (ARA) technique. Based on the nitrogenase activity, the selective highly efficient N₂ fixing isolates were further used for preparation of liquid formulation. A field experiment was conducted to study the effect of liquid formulation of endophytic nitrogen fixing consortium under graded levels of fertilizer nitrogen on sugarcane cv. CoM-0265. It was revealed that the inoculated treatments showed increased cane yield, top yield and CCS yield ranging from 7.80 to 16.34%; 14.02 to 54.72% and 11.60 to 27.91% respectively over the uninoculated control. It could be concluded that application of 25 % N ha⁻¹ + sett treatment of consortium @ 3 L ha⁻¹ + foliar application of consortium @ 3 L ha⁻¹ at 60 days after planting enhanced all growth parameters, cane yield, top yield, CCS yield and juice quality parameter of sugarcane crop. The results clearly indicated the possibility of saving fertilizer nitrogen to an extent of 75% (187.5 kg N ha⁻¹) i.e. 407.61 kg Urea ha⁻¹ and showed 7.80 to 16.34 % increase in yield of suru sugarcane crop by using a consortium of endophytic N₂ fixing bacterial inoculant. These endophytic bacteria can be recommended as bioinoculant for non legume crop like sugarcane which can help to reduce dependence on chemical nitrogen fertilizer and provide a step forward towards sustainable agriculture.

Key words: Endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria, liquid consortium, sugarcane.

Introduction

Endophytes are of agronomic interest as they can enhance plant growth in non-legume crops and improve the nutrition through nitrogen fixation (Boddey, *et al* 2003). Endophytic bacteria reside within the interior of plants without causing disease or forming symbiotic structures. Thus they inhabit various tissues of seed, roots, stem and leaves. Majority of them are non specific regarding their host preference which holds greater promises for plant growth promotion and increased yield in agriculturally important grasses such as sugarcane, rice, wheat, sorghum and maize. The endophytes produces phytohormones, plant growth promoting substances and could enhance the host plant's uptake of nutritional elements such as nitrogen and phosphorous.

Sugarcane is one of the most important cash crops in India. In general high inputs of nitrogen fertilizer to sugarcane are routine in India. The role of BNF in graminaceous plants begun to be elucidated with the discovery of the semi-solid N-free media by Dr. Johanna Döbereiner group's in the 1970s (Dobereiner *et al.*, 1972). Several diazotrophic species were isolated including the endophytes isolated from sugarcane plants growing in Brazil. These include *Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus*, *Herbaspirillum seropedicae*, *Herbaspirillum rubrisubalbicans*, *Azospirillum amazonense* and *Burkholderia* species (Baldani *et al.*, 1997; Döbereiner *et al.*, 1995; James, 2000). The role of such endophytic diazotrophic species on sugarcane growth, individually or in a complex endophytic community is very scanty. Few specific inoculation experiments are available on sugarcane (James and Olivares, 1998 and Muthukumarasamy *et al.*, 2002).

Nitrogen-fixing endophytic bacteria have edge over its rhizospheric counterparts because, being sheltered inside plant tissues, they face less competition and can make available the fixed nitrogen directly to plants (Gupta *et al.* (2012).

Interest of liquid biofertilizer formulations is growing rapidly all over the world since the liquid biofertilizers of good quality holds great promise in agriculture over the conventional carrier based biofertilizers. These liquid inoculants have longer shelf life, better survival, cost effective, convenience in handling, easy for storage and transport etc. Biofertilizers form an integral part of integrated plant nutrient supply system and organic farming which constitutes the

present as well as the future mandate of Indian agriculture. Much research has been done in India and abroad on different liquid formulations of *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum*, *Bradyrhizobium*, *Acetobacter*, P and K-solubilizers. However, research on development of technology of liquid endophytic nitrogen fixing bacterial inoculants is limited. A break through is needed in liquid inoculants technology for the endophytic nitrogen fixing bacterial consortium for sugarcane crop.

Liquid formulation is a recent technology in India and has very specific characteristics and uniqueness in its production methods. Liquid biofertilizers are the microbial preparations containing specific beneficial microorganisms which are capable of fixing or solubilizing or mobilizing plant nutrients by their biological activity (Chandra *et al.*, 2012).

Thus, with the view to isolate endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria and to asses functional potential in relation to plant growth promoting activities and nitrogen fixation in sugarcane crop a study was undertaken. These endophytic bacteria can be recommended as bioinoculant for non legume crop like sugarcane which can help to reduce dependence on chemical nitrogen fertilizer and provide a step forward towards sustainable agriculture. The potential use of endophytic bacterial inoculants has been reported in agriculture. Hence development of consortium of these N₂ fixing endophytes as liquid bioinoculant for sugarcane was undertaken.

Material And Methods

The present investigation was undertaken with the view to isolate endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria and to asses functional potential in relation to plant growth promoting activities, nitrogen fixation and effects on yield of sugarcane crop.

Collection of sugarcane samples

A total of eighteen sugarcane samples of CoM-0265 and Co-86032 varieties from different sugar recovery zones of Western Maharashtra were collected from selected district places for isolation of endophytic nitrogen fixing bacteria.

Isolation of endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria from sugarcane

The isolation of endophytic nitrogen fixing bacteria was carried out on selective media by enrichment culture technique and dilution and plating method (Aneja, 2003). The purified cultures of

all endophytes were maintained on the slants of respective selective media for further studies.

Morphological characterization

All the endophytic nitrogen fixing bacterial isolates were examined for their cell morphology, colony morphology and gram reaction as per the standard procedures given by Cappuccino and Sherman (1987).

Biochemical characterization

The isolates were subjected to biochemical characterization by employing the standard procedures given by Cappuccino and Sherman (1987). Different biochemical tests viz., Starch hydrolysis, H₂S production, Gelatin liquefaction, Catalase test, Oxidase test, Urease test were performed.

Functional diversity of endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria by Acetylene Reduction Assay (ARA)

The acetylene reduction assay (ARA) is an indirect method for measuring N₂-fixation at a time point (Hardy *et al.*, 1968). The functional diversity for N₂ fixation ability of all the endophytic bacterial isolates was determined by Acetylene Reduction Assay (ARA) technique. It is a highly sensitive and non-destructive method. The technique involves incubation of nitrogenase containing system (free-living bacteria) in a known atmosphere of acetylene (10% C₂H₂) in the gas phase, and after an optimum time of incubation (24 hrs), ethylene (C₂H₄) produced is measured by a gas chromatograph (Model: PERICROM-PR-2100) using flame ionization detector (FID). Based on the nitrogenase activity, the selective highly efficient N₂ fixing isolates were further used for preparation of liquid formulation.

Standardization of medium

The combinations were made by considering and comparing the ingredients and concentrations of respective selective media. Various combinations were made by considering the common ingredients, concentrations of ingredients, pH levels etc. Broth was made for each combination and devised as M1, M2, M3, M4, M5 and M6. By comparing *cfu* count on each devised media, where maximum *cfu* of all endophytes observed, was selected as standard appropriate medium for all endophytes. The medium M5 was found to be the most suitable for all the endophytes.

Liquid Formulation

The obtained efficient N₂ fixing bacterial endophytes were formulated for their mass production as a liquid consortium by comparing the selective media of these isolates and appropriate M5 medium was designed. The M5 medium was again formulated by using different concentrations of cell protectants like arabinose, trehalose, glycerol, PVP (poly-vinyl-pyrrolidone) and Fe-EDTA at various pH levels and was devised as LM1, LM2, LM3, LM4, LM5 and LM6. These media were tested and compared for growth by transferring 1% inocula of each endophyte and the flasks were incubated on rotary shaker at 110 rpm for 72 hrs. After incubation, a loopful culture was streaked on sterilized respective selective media plates. The plates were incubated at 28±1 °C and observed for growth. By comparing *cfu* count on each devised media, where maximum *cfu* of all endophytes was observed, was selected as standard appropriate endophytic consortium medium. The luxuriant cell count (*cfu*) of all the five endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria was observed on the LM3 medium as a consortium medium.

Shelf life of consortium

Shelf life studies of endophytic nitrogen fixing bacterial consortium was done after preparation of consortium by taking periodical cell count of all endophytes at monthly interval by serial dilution and plating method on respective selective media.

$$cfu/ml \text{ of consortium} = \frac{\text{Average plate count}}{\text{ml of sample}} \times \text{dilution factor}$$

Field Experiment:

NAAS Rating – 04.17

A field experiment was conducted (*Suru* plantation) in the experimental farm area of Department of Plant Pathology and Agril. Microbiology, MPKV, Rahuri to study the effect of liquid formulation of endophytic nitrogen fixing consortium under graded levels of fertilizer nitrogen on sugarcane cv. CoM-0265.

Sett treatment

Before planting, 10 months old sugarcane of cv. CoM-0265 were de-trashed and cut into 2 eye bud setts. These setts were inoculated with consortium @ 3 L ha⁻¹ by dipping them into requisite solution prepared from the consortium for about 15 to 20 minutes as per the treatments, while the uninoculated setts served as control.

Planting

Wet method of planting was followed. Furrows were irrigated and then the above treated sugarcane setts were planted in the furrows at 10 to 15 cm apart by pressing them 5-7 cm deep in the soil. Foliar application of consortium @ 3 L/ha at 60 days after planting was applied as per treatments.

Experimental details

A randomized block design (RBD) consisting four nitrogen levels with sett treatment of consortium (STC) @ 3 L/ha + foliar application of consortium (FAC) @ 3 L/ha at 60 days after planting (DAP), 100% RDF, endophytic bacterial consortium alone and consortium of VSI, Pune (Check) was followed. Thus, there were in all seven treatments which were replicated three times as given below.

T₁- 25% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 days after planting (DAP) to earthing up.

T₂- 50% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up.

T₃- 75% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up.

T₄- 100% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up.

T₅- Control (100% NPK/ha).

T₆- Consortium of VSI, Pune (Check).

T₇- Consortium alone (STC).

Plot size – 5m x 8m

Plot Area - 40 m²

Result And Discussion

The endophytic growth promoting bacteria with special reference to N₂ fixation from sugarcane of different sugar recovery zones of Maharashtra viz., High, Medium and Low recovery zones (varieties: Co-86032 and CoM-0265) were isolated and screened for nitrogenase activity. The isolates were identified on morphological and biochemical parameters. The standardization of liquid formulation and consortium of highly efficient endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria was carried in laboratory. The formulated liquid consortium was used in field study to assess its effect under graded levels of fertilizer nitrogen on sugarcane var. CoM-0265.

Isolation of endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria from sugarcane

Eighteen sugarcane samples from Co-86032 and CoM-0265 varieties were collected from different sugar recovery zones of Western Maharashtra and screened for the presence of endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria on selective culture media. A total of 77 endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria of *Gluconacetobacter* (16 isolates), *Burkholderia* spp. (14 isolates), *Herbaspirillum* spp. (17 isolates), *Azoarcus* spp. (15 isolates) and *Azospirillum* spp. (15 isolates) were isolated from Co-86032 and CoM-0265 sugarcane varieties (Table 1).

Several research workers have reported these beneficial microbes from different geographic regions. These results are in agreement with the findings of Cavalcante and Dobereiner (1998); Archana Suman *et al.*, (2001); Muthukumarasamy *et al.*, (2002) and Savalkar (2007) who isolated *Gluconacetobacter diazotrophicus* from roots, stem, juice of sugarcane. Reis *et al.*, (2004); Govindarajan *et al.* (2006) isolated endophytic *Burkholderia* spp. from sugarcane. Olivares *et al.*, (1996); Savalkar (2007); Asis *et al.* (2000); who isolated endophytic *Herbaspirillum* spp. from sugarcane, maize and sorghum. Savalkar (2007) who isolated endophytic *Azoarcus* spp.

from sugarcane. Baldani *et al.* (1984, 1986); Bashan *et al.*, (1991); Kirchof *et al.* (1997); Archna Suman *et al.*, (2001); Savalkar (2007); Gangwar and Kaur (2009) who isolated endophytic *Azospirillum* spp. from all parts of sugarcane.

Field experiment

A field experiment was conducted (*Suru* plantation) to study the effect of liquid formulation of endophytic nitrogen fixing consortium under graded levels of nitrogen on sugarcane cv. CoM-0265.

Growth parameters of sugarcane crop

The significant differences were observed between various treatments by applications of consortium under graded levels of nitrogen on all the growth attributing parameters, yield and juice quality parameter of sugarcane crop as compared to absolute control and the consortium alone.

Germination (%) at 30 DAP

The data reported in Table 2, revealed that significantly highest germination (58.59%) was recorded by application of consortium + 100% N/ha (T₄) followed by treatment T₃ (consortium + 75% N/ha); T₂ (consortium + 50% N/ha) and T₁ (consortium + 25% N/ha). However, these treatments were found to be statistically at par with each other. Minimum germination (52.44%) was recorded by the treatment T₅ (RDF). Among the consortia used, the endophytic N₂ fixing bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI consortium (check) and recorded 48.67 and 47.22% germination respectively.

Cane height (cm)

The application of consortium + 100% N/ha (T₄) recorded the maximum millable cane and top height (336.67 and 220.80 cm) followed by treatment T₃ (335.80 and 216.07 cm); T₂ (335.53 and 209.60 cm) and T₁ (332.47 and 201.33 cm). However, these treatments were found to be statistically at par with each other. Among the consortia used, the endophytic N₂ fixing bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI consortium (check) and recorded 315.80 cm and 308.93 cm millable cane height and 188.20 and 179.63 cm top height respectively (Table 2).

Number of Internodes cane⁻¹

There was significant difference due to application of consortium with graded levels of nitrogen on no. of internodes per cane presented in (Table 2). The number of internodes per cane were highest (27.73) due to application of consortium + 100% N followed by treatments T₃ (27.27); T₂ (26.60) and T₁ (25.73). However, these treatments were found to be statistically at par with each other. Among the consortia used, the endophytic N₂ fixing bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI consortium (check) with 23.67 and 22.67 number of internodes per cane respectively.

Cane girth (cm)

Similar trend of results were also observed regarding cane girth recorded at bottom, mid and top of canes wherein application of consortium + 100% N (T₄) recorded the maximum cane girth at bottom, mid and top (11.97, 10.95 and 9.98 cm) respectively with av. cane girth of 10.97cm followed by the treatment T₃ consortium + 75% N (11.67, 10.72 and 9.57 cm; av. cane girth 10.65 cm); T₂ (11.61, 10.55 and 9.31 cm; av. cane girth 10.49 cm) and T₁ (11.33, 10.46 and 9.28 cm; av. cane girth 10.36 cm). However, these treatments were found to be statistically atpar with each other. Among the consortia used, the endophytic N₂ fixing bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI consortium (check) recorded 9.82 and 9.74 cm av. cane girth respectively (Table 2).

Average cane and top weight (kg.cane⁻¹)

The results (Table 2) revealed that application of consortium + 100% N (T₄) recorded the maximum cane and top weight (2.966 and 0.383 kg.cane⁻¹ respectively) followed by the treatment T₃ (2.826 and 0.328 kg.cane⁻¹); T₂ (2.814 and 0.312 kg.cane⁻¹) and T₁ (2.740 and 0.307 kg.cane⁻¹). However, these treatments were found to be statistically at par with each other. Among the consortia used, the endophytic N₂ fixing bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI

consortium (check) and recorded 2.206; 0.231 and 2.077; 0.217 kg.cane⁻¹ av. cane and top wt. per cane respectively.

Number of Millable Canes ('000'.ha⁻¹)

The highest no. of millable canes (Table 2) was recorded by the treatment of application of consortium + 100% N (T₄) i.e. 109.75 '000'NMC.ha⁻¹ followed by the treatment T₃ () (106.58 '000'NMC.ha⁻¹); T₂ (102.83 '000'NMC.ha⁻¹) and T₁ (100.17 '000'NMC.ha⁻¹). However, these treatments were found to be statistically at par with each other. Among the consortia used, the bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI consortium (check) and recorded 95.83 '000'NMC.ha⁻¹ and 91.25 '000'NMC.ha⁻¹ no. of millable canes respectively.

These results are comparable with those of Oliveira *et al.* (2002), Muthukumarasamy *et al.*, (2002); Hari and Srinivasan (2005); Govindarajan *et al.*, (2006 and 2007); Oliveira *et al.*, (2002); Gangwar and Kaur (2009); Silva *et al.*, (2012) and Archna Suman *et al.* (2013) in sugarcane. The results showed a clear effect on the development of the inoculated plants, an increase in yield as compared to uninoculated plants.

Cane and top yield (t.ha⁻¹)

There were significant differences between the application of bacterial consortium along with graded levels of nitrogen on the cane, top and CCS yields.

The data reported in Table 3 revealed that the significantly highest cane yield and top yield (333.96 and 34.587 t.ha⁻¹) was recorded by application of consortium + 100% N/ha (T₄) followed by treatment T₃ consortium + 75% N/ha (327.52 and 30.378 t.ha⁻¹); T₂ consortium + 50% N/ha (321.58 and 28.021 t.ha⁻¹) and T₁ consortium + 25% N/ha (309.44 and 25.489 t.ha⁻¹). However, these treatments were found to be statistically at par with each other. The minimum cane yield and top yield (287.05 and 22.354 t.ha⁻¹) was recorded by the control RDF (100% NPK.ha⁻¹).

It was revealed from the yield data that the inoculated treatments showed increased cane yield over the uninoculated control ranging from 7.80 to 16.34%.

Among the consortia used, the bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI consortium (check) and recorded 265.61; 19.152 and 241.47; 16.587 t.ha⁻¹ of cane yield and top yield respectively.

It was interesting to note that all the inoculated treatments (T₁ to T₄) under graded levels of fertilizer nitrogen were found to be statistically at par with each other. These results clearly indicate the possibility of saving of fertilizer nitrogen to an extent of 75% (187.5 kg N ha⁻¹) i.e. 407.61 kg Urea ha⁻¹ and showed 7.80 to 16.34 % increase in yield.

CCS yield (t.ha⁻¹)

The data presented in Table 3 also revealed that significantly highest CCS yield (46.11 t.ha⁻¹) was recorded by the treatment T₄ i.e. application of consortium + 100% N/ha followed by treatments T₃ (44.43 t.ha⁻¹); T₂ (41.83 t.ha⁻¹) and T₁ (40.20 t.ha⁻¹). These treatments were found to be statistically at par with each other. The minimum CCS yield (36.05 t.ha⁻¹) was recorded by the control i.e. RDF (100% NPK.ha⁻¹). Among the consortia used, the bacterial consortium was found to be at par with the VSI consortium (check) and recorded 33.07 and 29.31 t.ha⁻¹ CCS yield respectively.

Similar trend of results were also reported by Muthukumarasamy *et al.*, (2002), Hari and Srinivasan (2005), Govindarajan *et al.* (2006), Singh *et al.*, (2007), Archna Suman *et al.* (2008 & 2013) and Silva *et al.*, (2012) who reported that application of *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum*, *Burkholderia*, *Herbaspirillum* and *Gluconacetobacter* alone or in combination under different levels of fertilizer nitrogen in sugarcane significantly improved the cane and sugar yield than the control.

Conclusion:

Thus, from the present study it could be concluded that application of 25 % N ha⁻¹ + STC @ 3 L ha⁻¹ + FAC @ 3 L ha⁻¹ at 60 days after planting enhanced all growth parameters, cane yield, top yield, CCS yield and juice quality parameter of sugarcane crop. It was interesting to note that all the inoculated treatments (T₁ to T₄) under graded levels

of fertilizer nitrogen were found to be statistically at par with each other. These results clearly indicated the possibility of saving fertilizer nitrogen to an extent of 75% (187.5 kg N ha⁻¹) i.e. 407.61 kg Urea ha⁻¹ and showed 7.80 to 16.34 % increase in yield of *suru* sugarcane crop by using a consortium of endophytic N₂ fixing bacterial inoculants. These endophytic bacteria can be recommended as bioinoculant for non legume crop like sugarcane which can help to reduce dependence on chemical nitrogen fertilizer and provide a step forward towards sustainable agriculture.

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Table 1. Isolation of endophytic N₂ fixing bacteria from different sugar recovery zones of Western Maharashtra.

Sr. No.	Loca-tion	Species of endophytic nitrogen fixing bacteria										Total isolates
		<i>Glucon- acetobacter</i>		<i>Burkholderia</i> spp.		<i>Herbaspirillum</i> spp.		<i>Azoarcus</i> spp.		<i>Azospirillum</i> spp.		
	Variety	86032	0265	86032	0265	86032	0265	86032	0265	86032	0265	
A) High recovery zone												
1	Kolhapur	GA-1	GA-2	Burk-1	Burk-2	Herb-1	Herb-2	Aar-1	Aar-2	Asp-1	Asp-2	10
2	Sangli	GA-3	GA-4	Burk-3	Burk-4	Herb-3	Herb-4	Aar-3	Aar-4	Asp-3	Asp-4	10
3	Satara	GA-5	GA-6	Burk-5	Burk-6	Herb-5	Herb-6	Aar-5	Aar-6	Asp-5	Asp-6	10
	Total	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	30
B) Medium recovery zone												
4	Pune	GA-7	GA-8	Burk-7	Burk-8	Herb-7	Herb-8	Aar-7	Aar-8	Asp-7	Asp-8	10
5	Nashik	GA-9	GA-10	Burk-9	-	Herb-9	Herb-10	Aar-9	Aar-10	Asp-9	Asp-10	09
6	Ahmednagar	GA-11	GA-12	-	Burk-10	Herb-11	Herb-12	Aar-11	Aar-12	Asp-11	Asp-12	09
	Total	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	3	3	3	28
C) Low recovery zone												
7	Solapur	GA-13	GA-14	Burk-11	Burk-12	Herb-13	Herb-14	-	Aar-13	Asp-13	-	08
8	Dhule	GA-15	-	Burk-13	-	Herb-15	Herb-16	Aar-14	-	-	Asp-14	06
9	Jalgaon	GA-16	-	-	Burk-14	-	Herb-17	-	Aar-15	Asp-15	-	05
	Total	3	2	2	2	2	3	1	2	2	1	19
Total isolates		09	07	07	07	08	09	07	08	08	07	77

* GA : *Gluconacetobacter*; Burk : *Burkholderia* spp.; Herb: *Herbaspirillum* spp.; Aar: *Azoarcus* spp.; Asp: *Azospirillum* spp.

Table 2. Growth parameters of sugarcane crop as influenced by liquid consortium under graded levels of fertilizer nitrogen

Treatments	Germination (%) at 30 DAP	Cane height (cm.cane ⁻¹)		Total cane height (cm)	No. of Inter-nodes.cane ⁻¹	Cane girth (cm) at			Av. cane girth (cm)	Av. Cane weight (kg/cane)		NMC ('000/ha)
		Millable	Top			Bottom	Mid	Top		Cane	Top	
T1- 25% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 days after planting (DAP) to earthing up	53.41	322.47	201.33	523.43	25.73	11.33	10.46	9.28	10.36	2.740	0.307	100.17
T2- 50% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up	53.67	335.53	209.60	545.67	26.60	11.61	10.55	9.31	10.49	2.814	0.312	102.83
T3- 75% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up	55.92	335.80	216.07	551.07	27.27	11.67	10.72	9.57	10.65	2.826	0.328	106.58
T4- 100% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up	58.59	336.67	220.80	557.25	27.73	11.97	10.95	9.98	10.97	2.966	0.383	109.75
T5- Control (100% NPK/ha)	52.44	318.33	196.13	514.50	24.07	11.17	10.43	8.96	10.19	2.679	0.265	98.42
T6- Consortium of VSI, Pune (Check)	47.22	308.93	179.63	488.50	22.67	11.16	9.97	8.08	9.74	2.072	0.217	91.25
T7- Consortium alone (STC)	48.67	315.80	188.20	506.33	23.67	10.50	10.38	8.57	9.82	2.206	0.231	95.83
SE±	2.11	6.08	6.16	9.40	0.65	0.20	0.16	0.25	0.15	0.114	0.009	3.14
CD at 5%	6.49	18.73	18.98	28.95	2.00	0.60	0.49	0.78	0.46	0.353	0.028	9.66

Table 3. Cane and CCS yield of sugarcane crop as influenced by consortium under graded levels of nitrogen

Treatments	Cane yield (t.ha ⁻¹)		CCS yield (t.ha ⁻¹)
	Cane	Top	
T1- 25% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 days after planting (DAP) to earthing up	309.44 (07.80)*	25.489 (14.02)	40.20 (11.60)
T2- 50% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up	321.58 (12.03)	28.021 (25.35)	41.83 (16.03)
T3- 75% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up	327.52 (14.10)	30.378 (35.89)	44.43 (23.25)
T4- 100% N/ha + STC @ 3 L/ha + FAC @ 3 L/ha at 60 DAP to earthing up	333.96 (16.34)	34.587 (54.72)	46.11 (27.91)
T5- Control (100% NPK/ha)	287.05	22.354	36.05
T6- Consortium of VSI, Pune (Check)	241.47	16.587	29.31
T7- Consortium alone (STC)	265.61	19.152	33.07
	SE±	8.98	1.24
	CD at 5%	27.68	3.84

* Figures in parenthesis denotes the per cent increase over control